

The Problem of Improving the Teacher's Professional Competence

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Abstract: An educator performs a responsible task along with the important and proud work of preparing our young generation to become worthy children of our nation. The article examines the problems of improving the professional competencies of educators, and presents the experience of working on the formation of professional competence of young educators through the implementation of the methodical support model.

Keywords: pedagogue, educator, competence, scientific activity, comprehensive development of the child, preschool education organization.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the main task of the educational process is to produce a competitive specialist for the society. According to the results of the research, most employers prefer to sign a contract with an employee who has the skills of independent study, quick and effective decision-making when necessary, and constant analysis (reflection) of his work. They see a slave. That is why the educator must first of all be educated, know the great life he lives, understand the laws of nature and society, be socially active, master general and preschool education pedagogy, children's psychology and physiology, and know the young characteristics of children. Also, the pedagogic educator's approach to the analysis of events from a scientific point of view makes it possible to realize the success of the comprehensive development of the child. For this purpose, the tasks of equipping the growing young generation with knowledge, restoring our spirituality, introducing them to world culture, masterpieces of our national culture, and raising them to be physically healthy and spiritually mature have been set. For this, the ability of each educator to demand and control himself is a guarantee of the fulfillment of the requirements set by our state for preschool education organizations.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

An educator performs a responsible task along with the important and proud work of preparing our young generation to become worthy children of our nation. The political maturity of an educator helps to realize his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of raising children, to approach educational tasks creatively, to constantly improve his skills and to grow his colleagues at work.

The teacher is the main person in the preschool education organization. The quality of all ideological and educational work and, moreover, the level of upbringing and knowledge of the future generation depends on the educator's ideological-political and scientific-

pedagogical preparation, sense of responsibility, pedagogical skills and creative attitude to work.

Competence requires constantly enriching one's knowledge, learning new information, feeling the demands of this day and age, the ability to search for new knowledge, process it and apply it in one's practical work. A competent specialist knows how to use the methods and methods that he has mastered in solving problems, which are suitable for this particular situation, he can selectively use the methods that are suitable for the current situation, reject those that are not suitable, acquires skills such as critical thinking.

Competent approach in pedagogy is not a completely new phenomenon, but its tributaries exist in continuously developing educational processes, and they are formed step by step. The issues of "skill", "competence", "competence", activity, and at the same time, the combination of a number of activities formed the basis of the scientific works of M.N.Skatkin, I.Ya.Lerner, V.V.Krayevsky, G.P.shchyedrovidsky, V.V.Davidov and other scientists of the field of pedagogy.

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, competence is "how the specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and "ownership of a plan of action in complex processes".

This includes:

- ✓ Maintaining and strengthening the child's health.
- ✓ Increase mental ability.
- ✓ Formation of beliefs and views that correspond to the ideological and mental principles of our national value and spirituality.
- ✓ Formation of love for motherland, social activity.

To inculcate the sense of friendship, honesty and hard work in the young generation.

An educator must have a high level of pedagogical skills, such as communication skills, thoroughly master the laws of pedagogical technique, speech, face, hand, leg and body movements, mime, gesture, pantomime). An educator should be able to observe children, correctly analyze the reasons for their behavior, and use tools that influence them.

In order to make the young generation aware of the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities, the educator must have the culture of speech and be able to reflect the following features in his speech.

- ✓ Clarity of speech.
- ✓ Voluntary speech.
- ✓ Purity of speech (free from its various dialect words), expression only in literary language, jargon (words specific to specialists in a certain profession or field), barbarism (words peculiar to other nations to the speech expressed in the language of a certain nation inappropriate use of z's), vulgarism (words used in actions, cursing) and conciliarism (speaking in a formal speech in inappropriate situations) and the speech of the pedagogue should be simple, fluent and understandable.

It is important to work on yourself and develop yourself in order to acquire professional and pedagogical competence. Self-development tasks are determined through self-analysis and self-assessment.

The formation of the professional competence of the teacher of preschool educational organizations is a combination of professional and general human relations, as a result of which it will be possible not only to effectively manage the educational process, but also to successfully solve the difficulties that arise during the performance of tasks. This undoubtedly affects the improvement of professional pedagogical competence and the development of pedagogical skills. At this stage of educational development, the competency-based approach is the leading direction in the activities of preschool teachers. The professional competence of educators of this preschool educational organization is the acquisition of experience, knowledge, skills, techniques and methods necessary for the accurate performance of the professional tasks of educators of preschool educational organizations.

The professional competence of a preschool teacher is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

- Social competence - ability to show activity in social relations, possession of skills, ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.
- Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activities, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, based on this competence, psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence is developed. is thrown into z. They contain the following content:
 - Psychological competence - healthy psychological in the pedagogical process.
 - Ability to create an environment, organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time;
 - methodical competence;
 - methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correctly defining the forms of educational or educational activity, being able to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, being able to use methods effectively, using tools successfully; informational competence;
 - search for, collect, sort, process necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and use it purposefully, appropriately, and effectively; creative competence;
 - a critical, creative approach to pedagogical activity, being able to demonstrate one's own creative skills; innovative competence-improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, putting forward new ideas on increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and effectively implementing them into practice;
 - Communicative competence - being able to have a sincere dialogue with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them.
 - Personal competence - to consistently achieve professional growth, to increase the level of competence, to demonstrate one's internal capabilities in professional activity.
 - Technological competence - assimilation of advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical BKM, ability to use modern tools, techniques and technologies.
 - Extreme competence - the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure), when pedagogical conflicts arise.

CONCLUSION

In short, by teaching in the class, interest in studying at school is cultivated in children, qualities such as a sense of responsibility, self-control, the habit of striving to work, and completing assigned work are formed. During the training, the skills of independent thinking are developed in children, great attention is paid to the development of skills such as listening to educators, distinguishing the main ideas of the story, and briefly summarizing. Through training in preparatory groups, skills such as initiative and independence, curiosity for knowledge, active thinking, comparison, generalization, drawing conclusions are cultivated in children.

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